

Synthesis of Possible Antiamebic Agents

R. MUKHOPADHYAY, D. GHOSH and B. PATHAK*

Department of Applied Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700009

Manuscript received 24 July 1973; accepted 9 April 1974

Some 4-dimethoxyphenylalkylaminoquinolines have been synthesised to examine their antiamebic activity.

It is well known that halo-8-hydroxyquinolines like vioform and diiodoquine possess antiamebic activity. 2-(2-Diethylaminoethyl)-3-*n*-propyl-4-chloro-5 or 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline¹ and

1-(2-*n*-hexyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-aminoethane² showed high *in vitro* antiamebic activity^{3,4}. R. Gopalchari⁵ prepared compounds of the type (I) with a view to observe their antiamebic activity. It is also known that some 4-aminoquinoline derivatives display antiamebic activity⁶.

(I)

(II)

(a)

(b)

The site of action of 8-hydroxyquinolines is likely to differ from that of dimethoxyphenylalkylamines. If, however, the same enzyme possesses two different active sites where the above two different types of compounds might act and if the geometry of the two active sites fits close to each other a compound of the type (II) will be more active than either the halo-8-hydroxyquinolines or dimethoxyphenylalkylamines. Based on this assumption compounds of the type (II) have been prepared to examine their antiamebic activity.

These compounds have been synthesised by the following route :

(IV), (V), (VII) or 4,7-dichloroquinoline $\xrightarrow{PH}$ (II)
(X = H; Y = H or Cl).

MUKHOPADHYAY, GHOSH & PATHAK : SYNTHESIS OF POSSIBLE ANTIAMEBIC AGENTS

Some of the compounds (II; X = Y = H; Z = OH) are halogenated by the interaction of ICl to yield monoiodo compound listed in Table 4.

Pharmacology: All these compounds were submitted to Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, India, for antiamebic testing. Report of testing is shown in the Table 1.

TABLE 1

Structure II						<i>In vitro</i> amoe- bacidal conc. ug/ml
A	B	P	X	Y	Z	
Me	H	(a)	H	H	OH	31.25
Me	Pr	"	H	H	OH	125
(CH ₂) ₂ N(Me) ₂	Pr	"	H	H	OH	125
H	H	"	H	Cl	H	—
Me	H	"	H	I	OH	—
			or	or		
			I	H		
Me	H	"	H	H	OMe	—
Me	Pr	"	H	H	OMe	—
Me	H	(b)	H	H	OH	—
Me	Pr	"	H	H	OH	125
(CH ₂) ₂ N(Me) ₂	Pr	"	H	H	OH	125
H	H	"	H	Cl	H	15.8
Me	H	"	H	I	OH	—
			or	or		
			I	H		
Me	H	"	H	H	OMe	—
Me	Pr	"	H	H	OMe	—
emetine hydrochloride						6.00

Experimental

2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline :

2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline¹ (0.03 mol) was demethylated by boiling with H₂SO₄ (0.88 mol) in the form of 70–75% solution for 6 hrs. The product was cooled, basified with NH₃ and

filtered. It was redissolved in HCl (1 : 1), treated with charcoal, basified with NH₃, filtered and washed thoroughly with water. It was recrystallised from dil. alcohol; m.p. 51°. (Found : C, 65.9; H, 5.72%. Calculated for C₁₃H₁₄ONCl : C, 66.24; H, 5.94%).

2-(2-Dimethylaminoethyl)-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-8-methoxy quinoline :

A mixture of 2-methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (0.03 mol), dimethylamine hydrochloride (0.03 mol), paraformaldehyde (1.8 g), absolute alcohol (50 ml) and conc. HCl (4 drops) was refluxed for 2 hrs on a water bath. A further amount of paraformaldehyde (1 g) was added and heating continued for another 2 hrs. Alcohol was removed. The residue was dissolved in water, basified with NaOH (2*N*) and the liberated base was extracted with benzene. The benzene layer was washed with water and dried over Na₂SO₄; on removal of benzene the base was obtained which was recrystallised from pet. ether (60°–80°), m.p. 74°–76°; yield 5 g. Picrate recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 185°. (Found : N, 12.5%. Calculated for C₂₃H₂₆O₃N₅Cl : N, 13.07%).

2-(2-Dimethylaminoethyl)-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-8-hydroxy quinoline :

The above compound (4 g) was demethylated by refluxing with HBr (48%, 40 ml) for 25 hrs. It was then basified with NH₃ and filtered. The precipitate was dissolved in HCl (1 : 1), treated with charcoal, basified with NH₃, filtered and the precipitate was washed well with water. Picrate recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 152°. (Found : N, 13.06%. Calculated for C₂₂H₂₄O₃N₅Cl : N, 13.43%).

1-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-1-aminohexane :

It was prepared by reductive amination of 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl-*n*-amyl ketone⁷.

TABLE 2

No.	(II; X = H)					m.p.°	Found : N %	Calculated for	N %
	A	B	P	Y	Z				
1.	H	H	(a)	Cl	H	140	6.98	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	7.02
2.	Me	H	(a)	H	OH	85	7.05	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₃ N ₃	7.10
3.	H	H	(b)	Cl	H	135	6.48	C ₂₅ H ₃₁ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	6.56
4.	Me	H	(b)	H	OH	75	6.57	C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₃ N ₃	6.63

Compounds 1 and 3 crystallised from benzene and 2 and 4 crystallised from alcohol.

TABLE 3

No.	(II; X = Y = H)				m.p.° (Hydro- chloride)	Found N %	Calculated for	N %
	A	B	P	Z				
5.	Me	Pr	(a)	OH	207–210	5.69	C ₂₇ H ₃₇ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	5.92
6.	(CH ₂) ₂ N(Me) ₂	Pr	(a)	OH	> 300	7.72	C ₃₀ H ₄₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	7.93
7.	Me	H	(a)	OMe	250(d)	6.09	C ₂₅ H ₃₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	6.29
8.	Me	Pr	(a)	OMe	149(d)	5.62	C ₂₆ H ₃₉ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	5.75
9.	Me	Pr	(b)	OH	> 300	5.32	C ₂₉ H ₄₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	5.59
10.	(CH ₂) ₂ N(Me) ₂	Pr	(b)	OH	160(d)	7.19	C ₃₂ H ₄₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	7.53
11.	Me	H	(b)	OMe	> 250(d)	5.63	C ₂₇ H ₃₇ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	5.92
12.	Me	Pr	(b)	OMe	145(d)	5.24	C ₃₀ H ₄₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	5.44

d = with decomposition.

Preparation of the Compound (II) :

A mixture of appropriate 4-chloroquinoline compound (0.005 mol), appropriate amine (0.005 mol) and phenol (2-4 ml) was heated in an oil bath at 160°-180° for 10-15 hrs. The mass was cooled, washed well with ether or chloroform to remove the reactants. Free bases were prepared by basification with dil. NH₃. Hydrochlorides recrystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ethyl acetate. Data of the compounds prepared are listed in Tables 2 and 3.

Iodination of 8-hydroxyquinolines of the type II :

To a solution of ICl (0.0025 mol) in glacial acetic acid, the solution of the compound (No. 2 or 4 of the Table 2) (0.00125 mol) in glacial acetic acid was added dropwise and the mixture was kept overnight.

TABLE 4

No.	P	m.p.°	Found : I%	Calculated for	I%
13.	(a)	190	24.1	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₂ I	24.42
14.	(b)	180	23.0	C ₂₆ H ₃₃ O ₃ N ₂ I	23.17

The mixture was then added to HCl (1:1). The separated solid was washed with dil. NH₃ and Na₂S₂O₃ solution. The product was recrystallised from dil. alcohol. Data enlisted in Table 4.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, India, and to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, India, for the pharmacological test report and for financial assistance as well as award of a fellowship to (R.M.) respectively.

References

1. K. L. PATHAK and B. PATHAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 231.
2. C. N. KACHRU and B. PATHAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 768.
3. Private communication.
4. Private communication.
5. R. GOPALCHARI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)*, 1960, **19C**, 296.
6. RHONE-POULENC. S.A. *Belg. Pat.* 618,068, Nov. 26, 1962.
7. D. GHOSH and B. PATHAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 673.